

A Comprehensive Analysis: Depression in Adolescents and Young Adults with Leukemia: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Background

This study focuses on the prevalence of depression among patients suffering from acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and acute myeloid leukemia (AML). These two forms of leukemia most commonly affect our target population: adolescents and young adult leukemia survivors (AYA-LS) – a population defined as individuals diagnosed with leukemia between the ages of 12 to 39 years old.

Although current literature has employed various assessment tools to evaluate comorbidities like depression and anxiety among LS, these measures have limitations. Such limitations include potential assessment bias stemming from oncologists' focus on pathology and psychiatrists' inability to address the distinct suffering experienced by this population fully. For this reason, this study recognizes the age-specific differences in cancer, particularly those diagnosed at a young age. Thus, emphasizing the importance of tailored approaches to address the mental health needs of AYA-LS. This consolidation and review of research holds the potential to advance support and intervention strategies, ultimately enhancing the mental health and overall quality of life for young adult leukemia survivors.

This study relies on electronic databases such as EBSCOhost, the British Journal of Cancer, PubMed, Google Scholar, and publications from the Saint James School of Medicine (SJSM).

KEY WORDS: Adolescents, Depression, Leukemia, Young Adults

1. INTRODUCTION

Depression and cancer (leukemia) are two medical conditions that continue to infiltrate the nooks and crannies of our homes, workplaces, and society as a whole. Whether it be directly or indirectly, everyone knows of someone who's been affected by either of the two. In today's society, it's relatively easy to incorrectly self-diagnose one's self as "depressed". We tend to adopt depression following any inconvenience in our lives, whether it be a low exam score, a breakup from a long-term friendship or relationship, or even a week-long bad hair "day". While each of the aforementioned is sufficient in fostering sadness, these reasons do not satisfy the characteristics of depression. The American Psychiatric Association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), defines depression as experiencing melancholy, a feeling of void, and becoming easily irritable. To be considered as clinical depression, symptoms must be consistent daily for two (2) or more weeks. These symptoms are often associated with a decreased ability to function regularly due to cognitive and somatic changes. On the other hand, we tend not to openly romanticize cancer as often as we do depression. We don't romanticize the latter at all. Unfortunately, some individuals aren't lucky enough to self-diagnose themselves with either, as these conditions are their harsh reality.

Both depression and cancer appear to intricately intersect in the lives of adolescents and young adults diagnosed with Leukemia. One-quarter (23%) of the AYA-LS who were medically assessed, were documented as having depressive symptoms. Additionally, 8% of this population met the criteria for a structured clinical interview diagnosis of depressive disorder (Tatsuo Akechi et al., 2022). Despite the myriad of leukemias that exist, some forms are more common in children, while other forms occur more frequently among adults. For this reason, this study focuses on acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and acute myeloid leukemia (AML), as these two forms most commonly affect our target population: adolescents and young adult leukemia survivors

(AYA-LS). (ALL) arises when lymphoid precursor cells undergo mutation, leading to dysregulated proliferation, survival, and accumulation of abnormal cells (Tedesco et. al 2012). This type of leukemia is the most prevalent cancer in childhood, as studies show that it accounts for 26.8% of cancer diagnoses among adolescents worldwide (Cheung et al. ,2015). In turn, the harsh bone marrow environment leads to a gradual decline in blood cell production, resulting in symptoms of fatigue, shortness of breath, bleeding, and susceptibility to infection (Wrench et. al 2022). In contrast, acute myeloid leukemia (AML), the more aggressive form of the two, mostly seen in young adults is marked by the clonal expansion of immature and defective myeloid cells and inhibition of normal hematopoiesis (Garza 2015). AML presents with anemia, thrombocytopenia, and impaired white blood cells.

As previously mentioned, this investigation primarily focuses on AYA-LS, a population defined as individuals diagnosed with leukemia between the ages of 12 and 39 years. These individuals confront a multitude of challenges, encompassing disruptions in education, careers, physical and social life, often accompanied by psychological distress, prominently depression. Existing literature speaks to the greater psychological distress that AYA-LS faces compared to other cancer survivor groups. To address the issue of depression effectively in patients with Leukemia, there is a critical need to consolidate and comprehensively review existing research articles. While there is no direct biological connection between leukemia and depression, numerous factors related to the disease and its treatment can significantly increase the likelihood of depression in leukemia patients. These patients encounter a range of challenges that affect various aspects of their lives. Research has shown that about 1/3 of AYA-LS experience psychological distress, and nearly 1 out of 4 experience depression. Furthermore, AYA cancer survivors face a higher risk of developing depression compared to both older cancer survivors and their cancer-free peers (Osmani et al. 2023). Cancer treatment can cause physical, social, and financial challenges for AYAs. Physical (e.g., hair loss and weight fluctuations) and biological changes (e.g., fertility issues) may reduce self-esteem and affect relationships, as these can all be emotionally and mentally taxing. Notably, corticosteroids, a key component of therapy for ALL, affect mood, behavior, and cognition (Hocchauser et. al 2005). Treatment schedules may interfere with educational and career goals, further compounding the financial distress endured by these patients and their families, as it hinders them from establishing stable and functional roles. While these repercussions generally contribute to higher distress during treatment, anxiety and depression symptoms may likely persist beyond treatment timeframes.

Longitudinal studies indicate a general decline in depressive symptoms over time, with improvements from the initial diagnosis phase into later stages of survivorship. Nevertheless, some survivors experience persistent depressive symptoms, particularly in the presence of unmet needs or other psychosocial challenges, which further exacerbate these symptoms (Osmani et al. 2023). Thus, it is vital to investigate long-term depression trajectories including how it evolves, its severity, and its interaction with leukemia treatments and survivorship experiences. Moreover, it is imperative to consider the broader aspects of their well-being, emotional health, and social functioning to gain an understanding of their unique journeys. This emphasizes the significance of our study, as its findings can provide valuable insights for affected patients, future researchers, and healthcare providers. These insights can inform the management of comorbid leukemia-related conditions, particularly depression, and address the evolving needs of AYA-LS. In doing so, we will open the door for future researchers to embark on a deeper exploration of the challenges faced by this population.

2. METHODS

This study acknowledges the frequent comorbidity of depression but takes care to draw from the literature that utilizes distinct scales for each condition. This approach allows for a focused analysis of depression and its specific association with childhood leukemia, maintaining the study's targeted scope. To ensure a comprehensive literature review, this study employs a variety of reputable sources. Electronic databases such as EBSCOhost, the British Journal of Cancer, PubMed, and Google Scholar will be utilized, alongside publications from the Saint James School of Medicine. Keywords including "adolescent," "mental health," "young adult," "depression," "leukemia," "acute lymphoblastic leukemia," "acute myeloid leukemia," "acute lymphoid leukemia," "AYA," and "diagnosis" will guide the search for studies examining the prevalence of depression among young people with leukemia.

This review applies clear inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria focus on studies involving leukemia patients between the ages of 12 and 39 who are either currently living with leukemia, are survivors, or are at different stages of the disease and suffer from depression. Exclusion criteria include patients aged > 39 and patients aged < 12 articles published before

2013, non-English language articles, and studies focusing on lymphomas. This systematic approach aims to provide a targeted and relevant synthesis of research on depression in AYA with leukemia.

To identify articles that met our inclusion and exclusion criteria, researchers collaboratively screened titles and abstracts for eligibility. Following this initial screening, a designated researcher further conducted secondary screening to confirm that the selected articles were available in full text. This ensured that the research team could proceed with a comprehensive analysis of each article, allowing for the extraction of relevant information in alignment with the study objectives.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1. Prisma flowchart.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies included.

<i>Author</i>	<i>Publication Year</i>	<i>Region of Study</i>	<i>Control Characteristics</i>	<i>Age at Cancer Diagnosis</i>	<i>Depression Scale</i>
Aili et al	2021	Sweden	Siblings control	Adolescence	BDI-II
Akechi et al.	2021	Japan	Cancer individuals free	12-39 years	BDI-II/CDI/HADS
Baytan et al	2016	Turkey	Siblings control	NR	KCDI
Chevalier et al	2023	USA	No reference group	21 years	PRIME-MD/SCID
Forster et al	2022	UK	No reference group	13-24 years	HADS
Kim et al	2022	USA	General population	Adolescence	CES-DC
Park, Rostentein	2015	USA	Cancer individuals free	15-29 years	NR
Wolfson et al	2017	USA	Non-CCC	15-39 years	NR
Osmani	2023	Global	General Population	15-39 years	Various
Saadi et al.	2024	Oman	Non-reference group	12-18 years	CES-DC
Geue et al	2019	Germany	Cancer individuals free	18-39 years	HADS
Sun et al.	2019	China	No reference group	15-39 years	PHQ-9
Niedzwiedz et al.	2019	Global	No reference group	All ages	Various
Sansom-Daly, Wakefield	2013	Global	General Population	15-39 years	HADS/PHQ-9
Myers et al.	2014	USA	Normative population	12-15 years	BASC
Batson et al.	2016	USA	Normative population	12-18 years	CBCL/ HADS
Bin Lee et al.	2023	Global	Various	12- 25 years	Various

Abbreviations: Behavior Assessment System for Children, BASC; Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale, CES-D; Child Behavior Checklist, CBCL; Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, HADS; Primary Care Evaluation of Mental Disorder, PRIME-MD; Kovacs Children Depression Inventory, KCDI; Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV, SCID; Beck’s Depression Inventory -2, BDI-II; Patient Health Questionnaire-9, PHQ-9; Not reported in study, NR; Non- Comprehensive Cancer Center, non-CCC.

Table 2. Meta-analysis on the prevalence of depression among AYA cancer survivors (11 studies, 7293 participants)

Study (year)	Depression cases	Total	Prevalence
Aili et al. (2021)	222	227	0.98
Baytan et al(2016)	16	100	0.16
Chevalier et al.(2023)	60	249	0.24
Forster et al.(2022)	175	820	0.21
Kim et al. (2022)	445	1106	0.4
Saadi et al(2024)	52	92	0.57
Geue et al(2019)	160	502	0.32
Sun et al (2019)	96	249	0.58
Myer et al (2014)	114	159	0.72
Batson et al (2016)	45	159	0.28
Akecki et al.	174	3559	0.05
Random effects model		7293	0.3790

Table 3. Risk, protective and exacerbating factors of psychological symptoms in AYAs.

Study	Duration of study	Cancer and treatment	Family and environmental factors	Patient factors
Saadi et al	Up 9 months after diagnosis	Stage of cancer: The higher stage had elevated depression than the lower stage. Having chemotherapy and transplant/radiotherapy has a higher depression score	Family support: "Unsupportive": higher depression "Supportive" have a higher depression	Age at diagnosis: Adolescents had a significantly higher depression than young adults. Aware of diagnosis: Adolescents aware of diagnosis had elevated depression
Geue et al.	Up to 4 years after diagnosis (2-year period)	No relevant mediators and reported	Family support: "Unsupportive": higher depression "Supportive" have a higher depression	Female sex: Significantly higher depression than the male sex

Sun et al.	At the time of diagnosis	Stage of cancer: Higher stage had insignificantly higher depression Having stem cell transplant: higher depression than chemotherapy S	Marital status: "Single" significantly higher depression than "married"	Physical Comorbidity: Significantly higher depression than those without comorbidity. Pessimistic Personality: significantly higher depression than those without
Myers et al.	Up to 12 months after diagnosis	No relevant mediators and reported	Family support: "Unsupportive": "Supportive" have significantly higher depression. Marital status of parents: "Not married" has significantly higher depression than married (OR=2.36; p=0.017)	Age at diagnosis: School age(12 years)' had insignificantly lower depression
Kunin-Batson et al.	Up to 12 months after diagnosis	Having a neurological event during therapy had a significantly higher depression than those without (OR=2.99; p=0.042)	Family support: "Unsupportive": "Supportive" have significantly higher depression than healthy functioning (OR=2.62, p=0.024). Marital status of parents: "Unmarried" had insignificantly lower anxiety than 'married'	Age at diagnosis: 'School age (12 years) had insignificantly lower depression Sex: Males had insignificantly lower depression than females

Overall 41,704 records were identified from databases (Figure 1). Duplicates were removed leaving 11,600 articles to be screened for title and abstract, with the remaining 7,160 selected for further screening. After reading 150 full-text articles, 17 articles were eligible for inclusion in this systematic review.

Study characteristics

The review characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The majority of the studies were conducted in the United States (29.4%) and Global population (23.5%). Of the studies reviewed, five were cross-sectional, 4 cohort, 3 empirical reviews, 2 longitudinal, 2 meta-analyses, and 1 validation. The majority of studies (82.4%) had less than 500 participants. These studies included patients diagnosed with ALL or a general diagnosis of leukemia. The remaining 6 studies focused on multiple cancer types. The participants were recruited from cancer registries and the general population. The studies included participants who were either on treatment or off treatment post-diagnosis.

Depression Prevalence

Eleven studies reported on the prevalence of depression among AYAs, with prevalence ranging from 5% to 98%. The most frequently used instrument is the Hospital Anxiety and depression scale(HADS). The prevalence of depression among the 7,293

AYAs from the multiple studies was 38% (Figure 2). Reviewed studies underscored a threefold increase in major depressive disorder (MDD) risk in AYA cancer patients (HR, 3.12; 95% CI, 2.64–3.70)(Tatsuo Akechi et al., 2022).

Risk and Exacerbating Factors of Depression

The risk, protective, and exacerbating factors of depressive symptoms were summarized and reported in Table 3. Amongst studies that compared the different stages of cancer, an increase in depressive symptoms was found in AYAs with an advanced cancer diagnosis (Al-Saadi et al, 2014, Sun et al, 2019). In terms of demographic factors, AYA survivors who had undergone intensive treatments such as inpatient chemotherapy were at particularly high risk for MDD (HR, 0.43; 95% CI, 0.30–0.62)(Lydia Chevalier et al., 2023). Sun et al reported that patients living with additional comorbidities reported increased depression symptoms. All of the studies, except one, reported that there was no difference in depressive symptoms between different cancers (Akechi et al, 2022, Geue et al, 2019). In regards to the patient's family dynamic and environment, having a healthy support system was consistently found to significantly reduce the risk of depressive symptoms. Myers et al. reveal a significant increase in depression in patients whose parents are not married, while Kunin-Batson et al. report no significant increase.

In comparison with their cancer-free peers, the risk of experiencing depression symptoms was higher in AYA-LS. Two studies comparing AYA-LS with siblings found that there was an increased risk of depression in AYA-LS (Aili et al, 2021, Baytan et al, 2014). Additionally, Akechi and colleagues reported that the odds of depression were higher in AYAs compared with older LS. Park et al. found that younger age is associated with increased rates of psychological distress and psychiatric symptoms.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on our findings AYA with leukemia have a notably high rate of depression, which provides considerable issues for both patients and clinicians. The adolescent population, defined as people aged 12 to 17, face particular psychosocial challenges as a result of their cancer diagnosis, such as increased despair and psychological discomfort. These individuals are six times more likely to be diagnosed with cancer than those aged 18-39 demonstrating the comparatively high incidence and early effect of cancer in this age range. According to Akechi et al., the emotional weight of a life-threatening diagnosis, such as cancer, is sufficient to cause depressive symptoms. Not only are patients frightened by their diagnosis, but their usual lives are also abruptly disrupted. These disturbances affect social activities, schooling, and career plans. Most cancer patients have a painful emotional response; nevertheless, some develop severe depression. A leukemia diagnosis, with its tremendous physical demands, results in a complex interplay between physical symptoms and mental health in these young people. Depression, in particular, is a prevalent issue that is sometimes aggravated by factors such as severe physical symptoms during chemotherapy (e.g., nausea and vomiting), cancer pain, and other side effects that last throughout various stages of cancer treatment (Park, 2015).

Patients diagnosed with leukemia find themselves under great burden whether that be related to pain and physical suffering, sexual and fertility issues, body image concerns, mental health challenges, and/or psychological issues. Our studies have disclosed that AYA leukemia patients have reported far more elevated symptom burden in comparison to older adults. Indefinitely, this younger group has reported more pain in general, inclusive of pain across treatment stages, i.e. during active treatment, survivorship, and in advanced or incurable phases. These symptoms contribute to a decline in the quality of life and overall mental well-being of these individuals (Park 2015). A prospective study writes that depressive symptoms in AYA begin from the end of the first month of therapy through 12 months post-diagnosis (Myers et al. 2014). Cancer patients with depression are more likely to have poor adherence to treatment, which can lead to prolonged hospitalization. These patients who are exposed to long hospitalization are more likely to experience an increasing rate of mortality and suicidal ideations. (Akechi et al, 2022). This empathizes with the importance of social and psychological support that AYA leukemia survivors need. Depression is a common comorbid condition in these patients and symptoms often present for at least a year following diagnosis.

The human mind is power and our psychological capacity or lack thereof will result in two categories with a wide spectrum. The wide spectrum includes the growth of mental maturity, which yields successful coping mechanisms or the inability to thrive. AYA-LS, specifically within the younger range of 12-17 years, tend to suffer from the latter as they view their cancer as more unexpected and overwhelming, and thus, experience more psychological maladaptation (Sun et al, 2019, Sansom-Daly et al, 2013). Young people's underdeveloped coping skills can also interfere with their capacity to successfully navigate the demands of the cancer experience (Sansom-Daly et al, 2013). According to research, depression is most severe during the acute period and

diminishes following therapy, depending on the stage of diagnosis. Depressive symptoms continue and vary from person to person, even if these statistics demonstrate a decrease in the prevalence of depression throughout therapy. Among the several risk factors that have previously been identified, a lack of strong social support may be the primary reason for this persistence (Niedzwiędz et al. 2019).

Several studies revealed the crucial role that social support and environmental factors play in the development of depression among adolescent LS. Adolescents are more likely than young adults to experience the compounded emotional toll of leukemia. The reason being, that younger LS experience greater restriction of their participation in social activities due to health concerns. Such isolation can foster poor social development, alongside exacerbated feelings of anxiety and depression. Subsequently, this isolation can hinder social development, further reinforcing the need for targeted interventions that address both psychological and social aspects of recovery. Unfortunately, repercussions may extend beyond academic skills, encompassing a range of missed opportunities, such as participation in sports, group activities, excursions, and award ceremonies, as well as the absence of daily structure and routine provided in the scholastic environment. Prolonged absences from school and limited peer interaction can contribute to the development of emotional, behavioral, and psychological challenges (Al-Saadi et al, 2024). This limited peer interaction, in particular, may foster false perceptions of a poor support system among adolescents, as they rely heavily on approval from their peers during this stage in life. On a larger scale, when analyzing AYA-LS holistically rather than two separate sub-groups (i.e., group 1: adolescents and group 2: young adults) studies express that unmarried parents, poor physical functioning, and low social support are linked to higher depression scores (Myers et al., 2014). As noted in Table 3, Sun et. al reveal that AYA-LS who are products of single-parent homes display greater depression levels compared to those whose parents have gotten and/or remained married. This supports the notion that the relationship between family functioning and quality of life varies, exhibiting both positive and negative correlations.

Moreover, limitations in healthcare resources, such as the dire lack of mental health professionals, may further hinder access to psychological support services for leukemia patients. Additional research has shown that a healthy family environment is a strong protective factor against the development of these disorders, as well as improving the quality of life of children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer. Such findings are further supported in an Oman-based study. In this study, Al-Saadi et al. (2024) state that support extended by family members and friends to Leukemia patients significantly reduces mental distress and alleviates the adverse side effects associated with cancer treatment.

In a study involving 3,559 adolescent and young adult (AYA) cancer survivors in Japan, particularly those with leukemia, researchers observed significantly lower health-related quality of life (HRQoL) scores—especially in areas of general health and emotional functioning—compared to their siblings (Aili et al., 2021). For AYA leukemia survivors specifically, HRQoL outcomes, including general health and emotional well-being, were notably lower than both sibling scores and established normative data, with survivors at increased risk for mental health challenges like depression (Baytan et al., 2016). Associations between HRQoL, self-efficacy, and social support highlight the importance of psychosocial factors in recovery. Stronger social support and higher self-efficacy were correlated with better HRQoL in survivors, while these factors were less critical for cancer-free siblings, suggesting different psychosocial needs within this population (Akechi et al., 2022). Furthermore, delays in cancer diagnosis among AYA patients negatively affect HRQoL and mental health, as the delay may increase vulnerability to depression. These delays often stem from a complex interaction of factors, including misinterpreted symptoms due to age, healthcare system complexities, and delayed referrals. Extended diagnostic uncertainty can worsen distress and diminish HRQoL, as untreated symptoms disrupt daily life. Addressing the factors contributing to diagnostic delays is crucial for better health outcomes, potentially improving both HRQoL and mental well-being in AYA cancer patients (Foster et al., 2022).

Multiple analyses have shown that having a marital status of single, a pessimistic mindset or outlook on life, and having additional concurrent stressful life events along with other physical comorbidities were confirmed to be independently associated with a higher occurrence of depression. It has been consistently identified that physical as well as cognitive impairments via physical symptoms/treatment complications could lead to more psychological difficulties and these individuals are affected more significantly and more frequently than patients without any comorbidities (Sun et al, 2019). Moreover, the risk of developing depression as a comorbidity is significantly higher among AYAs with metastatic cancer (HR, 6.73; 95% CI, 3.65–12.40) and leukemia (HR, 6.30; 95% CI, 3.75–10.58) (Tatsuo Akechi et al., 2022). These statistics suggest that the presence of leukemia heightens the risk for depression in AYAs when compared to other cancer diagnoses.

In order to promote early diagnosis, regular mental health screenings in oncology settings should be introduced, given the distinct risk profile of AYA cancer survivors. Continuous support may also lessen the symptoms of chronic depression (Osmani, 2023). Furthermore, it is important to note that people who suffer from cancer may not suffer from depression. For those patients, a deeper appreciation for life and a reassessment of personal priorities might result from the short-term psychological alterations that some people experience after receiving a cancer diagnosis (Niedzwiedz et al., 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, our hypothesis states that adolescents (12-17 years) would be more likely to develop depression while young adults (18-39 years) are less likely. This was originally suspected because adolescents are thought to have fewer responsibilities and exogenous stressors when compared to young adults who are concerned about family dynamics, finances, careers, and so on. However, based on our comprehensive review, it was found that adolescents with leukemia have a greater predisposition to developing depression compared to young adults with leukemia. This is due to the current life phase of adolescents which is fragile and of tremendous significance in terms of social, physical, and psychological development. Leukemia places a burden and limitation on key aspects of the adolescent's life. Activities such as sports and certain social gatherings are no longer recommended, attendance for school most likely will cease or greatly decrease and their adolescent years become engulfed by hospital visits, chemotherapy, medications, and surgeries. Studies have shown that this drastic, sudden change in lifestyle is overwhelming for this age range and they tend to cope less efficiently leading to an increased prevalence of depression. Therefore, we must reject our hypothesis.

6. LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH

A limited number of articles focused exclusively on ALL and AML as the primary cancer, with most research covering a broader range of cancer types. The majority of studies made comparisons either between adolescents and children or between AYAs and older adults. One significant limitation encountered was the presence of language barriers within the initial pool of studies reviewed.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS OF FUTURE RESEARCH.

The authors of this study acknowledge that a substantial amount of existing literature fails to further compare adolescents to young adults who are leukemia survivors. For this reason, it may be more beneficial for this population if future researchers explore the similarities and/or differences between leukemia survivors within their group as opposed to their cancer-free or older peers. In doing so, more efficient and age-appropriate treatment can be exercised on these patients, possibly reducing a portion of the stress they bear.

Furthermore, findings based on existing literature stress the importance of routine mental health screenings for LS. Routine screening may lead to early detection and intervention of depressive symptoms among this population.

8. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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